

**FLEXURAL FATIGUE AND FRACTURE
OF UNIDIRECTIONAL GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES
AT LOW TEMPERATURES**

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue behavior under flexural loading of unidirectional graphite/epoxy composites at several low temperatures has been studied. Reported measurements include the flexural moduli, yield stress, and fracture stress at temperatures from 20 to -40°C following 10^5 load cycles between approximately 20 and 80 percent of yield strength. Also, a summary is reported of the measurements procedure. Observations via scanning electron microscope (SEM) of the fracture surfaces are included. Upon fatigue loading, the strength, albeit scattered, increases with decreasing temperatures. However, the flexural moduli degraded with lower temperatures. The results are explained in terms of the influences of competing factors such as change of the constituents' thermoelastic properties and stresses at low temperatures. Finally, a simple phenomenological model is presented to explain the fracture development, which is based upon the competition between the building up of tensile stresses and relaxation of compressive stresses following microfractures, and it leads to the low temperature's effects on the microstructural scale of the material.

Keywords: Composite, composite failure, composite fatigue, composite fracture, flexural fatigue, graphite/epoxy, microfracture

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper summarizes the results of an experimental study on the behavior of unidirectional graphite/epoxy composites subjected to flexural fatigue and fracture over a temperature range of 20° to -40°C . Numerous literatures show that the fatigue behavior and damage accumulation in fiber composites have been well studied for room temperature and higher service temperatures, but very little data exist for low-temperature regimes, especially for the temperature regimes of the terrestrial cold regions. Basic failure mechanism in composite laminates includes inter- or intralaminar matrix cracking, interface failure, and fiber fracture. Temperature reduction results in a stiffer and more brittle matrix and can potentially influence these failure mechanisms. The objective of this study is to understand how the damage state, stiffness, strength, and fatigue properties of composite laminates are influenced by the reduction of temperatures.

The yield strength of a composite laminate is a reliable measure of the internal damage as proven by Roylance et al. (1983). Therefore, in this study the yield point was used as the basis for damage development comparisons under different temperatures. Each fatigue specimen was subjected to 10^5 flexural load cycles between 20 and 80 percent of the expected yield strength. Modulus changes were determined at several intervals as the fatigue cycling progressed. The flexural strength was determined upon completion of 10^5 cycles by loading the composite specimen in flexure in a four-point flexural bending test fixture. Failure surfaces were examined under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to detect failure modes. Results of tests performed at different temperatures were then compared to determine temperature effects.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental results were obtained from T300/Fiberite-975 graphite/epoxy panels of uni-directional lay-up. The material was prepared in the laboratory from 305- by 305-mm (12- by 12-in.) panels of 16-ply thickness. The test specimen was formed as a coupon (17.8-mm in width x 229-mm in length) with fibers oriented in longitudinal direction. All specimens were X-rayed to ensure that they were free from internal defects. Defective specimens were rejected from the tests. To avoid moisture absorption, all specimens were maintained in a sealed container until before testing. Small samples were tested periodically to ascertain that the moisture content was unaltered.

Four-point flexural tests were performed at 20° , 0° , -20° , and -40°C to establish the flexural modulus and loads associated with yield and failure. Figure 1 is a schematic of the loading mechanism. The four-point loading apparatus consisted of four 6.35-mm-diameter (0.25-in.) rollers. Although the lower two rollers were fixed, the upper two were free to pivot about the x-axis (parallel to the length of the specimen). This configuration ensured that any twisting of the specimen was not transmitted as a side load, and it also accounted for

Figure 1. Test schematic.

any small deviations in thickness across the sample. The loading system was actuated by a computer-controlled electrohydraulic machine. All tests were performed in a nitrogen gas-cooled environment chamber. Temperatures within the chamber were controlled and held to $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ of the predetermined test temperatures by a cooled nitrogen gas, the flow of which was varied by a thermostatically controlled solenoid valve.

The flexural modulus of elasticity, E (Pa), and the flexural strength, S (Pa), were calculated from the following equations:

$$E = \frac{Pa(3L^2 - 4a^2)}{4bh^3d} \quad (1)$$

$$S = \frac{3Pa}{bh^2} \quad (2)$$

where

- P = load (N)
- a = distance between the closest support and the load roller (m)
- L = support span (m)
- b = specimen width (m)
- h = specimen thickness (m)
- d = vertical deflection of the specimen center (m)

Tests for fatigue-by-flexure were conducted over the same temperature range as the flexure-to-failure tests. For all low- temperature testing, specimens were placed in the environment chamber and allowed to cool to the desired temperature for at least one hour before testing. Each specimen was subjected to 10^5 flexural sinusoidal loadings at a frequency of four Hz within the limits of 20 percent and 80 percent of the estimated yield load. This frequency is well below ten Hz, at which hysteresis heating is known to develop for this type of material. To obtain damage accumulation estimates through stiffness data, load-deflection characteristics were recorded from separate quasi-static flexure tests performed on the samples at the beginning, mid-point, and end of the fatigue cycle. The maximum load applied during the quasi-static tests was limited to the 80 percent of the estimated yield load. Upon completion of fatigue cycle and corresponding quasi-static test at 10^5 cycles, flexure-to-failure tests were performed at the specified temperatures.

Load and deflection for all quasi-static tests were recorded on a digital recorder at a rate of 200 samples per second. The cross-head speed was 1.22 mm/s (0.05 in./s). Load was recorded directly as voltage outputs from the electrohydraulic loading system, and the deflection was read through an auxiliary cantilever extensometer specially fabricated and calibrated at low temperatures.

Table 1 summarizes the results of flexural tests of all nonfatigued and fatigued systems.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fracture Process

In all of the flexure-to-failure tests at all temperatures, the fatigued composite exhibited a reduction of both the elastic modulus and the yield

Table 1. Results of flexural failure tests

Temperature (°C)	20	0	-20	-40
<u>Nonfatigued specimens</u>				
Modulus (GPa)				
Before yield	161 (6.93)	164 (8.84)	158 (12.1)	156 (3.66)
After yield	153 (6.67)	158 (11.0)	149 (15.7)	151 (2.57)
Strength(GPa)				
Yield	1.26 (0.09)	1.46 (0.16)	1.36 (0.28)	1.35 (0.08)
Failure	1.60 (0.12)	1.73 (0.09)	1.76 (0.13)	1.58 (0.11)
<u>Fatigued Specimens</u>				
Modulus (GPa)				
Before yield	160 (4.36)	154 (12.0)	154 (7.95)	154 (5.63)
After yield	122 (8.62)	117 (12.1)	99.3 (11.4)	109 (12.8)
Strength (GPa)				
Yield	1.31 (0.14)	1.34 (0.15)	1.32 (0.14)	1.28 (0.09)
Failure	1.61 (0.04)	1.82 (0.09)	1.92 (0.09)	1.96 (0.10)
Note: Figures within parenthesis represent the standard deviations of the values. Each data set represents the average of ten tests.				

(a) Failure in static flexure test at -20°C (nonfatigued specimen)

(b) Failure in static flexure test at -20°C (fatigued specimens).

Figure 2. Load and deflection results in four-point flexure tests.

strength. The net effect of these results was toughening of the material. The load-deflection curves displayed slight concave curvature initially indicating an increase in stiffness; beyond this point the curve is essentially straight, the slope of which characterizes the flexural stiffness. Figure 2 [(a) and (b)] illustrates this behavior for one series of tests. The point of departure from linearity was defined as the yield point, and the stress computed from equation 2 was accepted as the yield strength. In the series of tests illustrated by Figure 2, yielding occurs at approximately 2900 N for the nonfatigued specimens, as compared to 2400 N for fatigued specimens. Note also that although both types of specimens experience failure at approximately 3200 N, the fatigued specimens exhibit plastic behavior over a greater range of deflections.

Failure by flexure occurred through initial crushing of the area above the neutral plane, occasionally accompanied with interlaminar shear and finally by tensile fracture through the remaining thickness to the bottom surface. The failure sequence is shown schematically in Figure 3. The yielding (for nonfatigued and fatigued conditions) begins with the growth of incipient interlaminar shear crack in the upper compressive region, mostly away from the neutral axis. Note that the compressive modulus of this composite is about 87 percent of its tensile modulus. With increased loading the number as well as dimensions of these cracks in the compression zone grow as shown in Figure 3(b). The mode of failure is primarily by microbuckling as modeled by Rosen (1965). The net effect of this progressive failure of the fibers in the compression zone is shifting of the neutral axis more and more in the zone previously dominated by tensile stresses as shown by the arrow in Figure 3(c). Remembering that Rosen's model, whether it considers the extensional mode represented by equation 3, or the shear mode represented by equation 4, below, the compressive strength, S_c , is always a function of matrix stiffness E_m or G_m , which are greatly influenced by the temperature.

$$S_c(T) = 2V_f \left[\frac{V_f E_m(T) E_f}{3(1 - V_f)} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$S_c(T) = \frac{G_m(T)}{1 - V_f} \quad (4)$$

where V_f = volume fraction of the fiber.

Figure 3(d) shows the development of one or more major shear cracks in the plane of the lamina. The neutral axis shifts further down and fresh fiber failures in microbuckling mode continue until the outer fiber tensile stress exceeds the fiber strength, when the mixed mode crack connecting both the tensile and the compressive zones catastrophically passes through the entire thickness of the specimen splitting it into two. Although at the beginning of loading the ratio of thickness between the compressive zone (h_1) and (h_2) was only 0.87, this ratio increased to 2.3 at the final failure [see Figure 3 (e)].

Observed under the scanning electron microscope (see Figure 4), 60 to 70 percent of the fracture surface exhibited compression failure. This type of failure is recognized by a light and smooth texture with clumps of short broken fibers lodged in a disorderly fashion to the substrate of well-ordered material. In contrast, the tensile failure zone is darker with abundant evidence of fiber pullouts. As stated before, the relatively large surface area under compressive failure was expected due to the strength being substantially lower in compression than in tension.

The above explanation is presented purely from the close observation of the failure phenomena happening during the loading. Owen and Morris (1970 a, b) also observed initiation of similar failures on the compressive surface of four-point bending tests involving high-modulus graphite/epoxy fibers. In their cases also the successive buckling of adjacent layers shifted the neutral axis further down to bring more areas of the section under compressive stress.

The results of the flexure tests of the nonfatigued specimens are illustrated in Figure 5 (a) and (b), and those of the fatigued specimens in Figure 6 (a) and (b).

3.2 Stiffness

As mentioned before, a close examination of initial portions of load deflection curves of all fatigued and nonfatigued samples [Figure 2 (a) and (b)] shows a slight but discernible stiffness increase. This is attributed primarily to fiber

Figure 3. Schematic representing the failure sequences in flexure.

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrograph of the through-the-thickness fracture surface.

(a) Modulus

(b) Strength

(c) Modulus comparison

Figure 5. Low-temperature flexural performance data of the nonfatigued specimens.

as temperatures decrease, is responsible for the initial overall stiffness increase of the composite. With further cooling, the thermoelastic residual stresses (resulting from the thermal expansion mismatch between the fibers and the matrix) may have exceeded the matrix strength and allowed debonding and transverse microcracks in matrix to develop. The development of such microcracks by mere cooling has been documented earlier by Dutta and Farrell (1988) through acoustic emission studies and by others by microscopic examination of the cracks (Cohen et al., 1984). The effect of these microcracks would be a reduction of the laminate's stiffness.

straightening from some initial curvature when subjected to tension. The phenomenon of fiber straightening is not uncommon. In fact, existence of a certain degree of curvature in a large percentage of fibers has been considered to be one of the main reasons of the degradation of tensile strength of unidirectional fiber composites at low temperatures (Dutta, 1992). Madhukar (1993) also has reported observing fiber curvatures in many graphite/epoxy composites.

The next portion of the load deflection curve for all samples was essentially linear to the yield point. Beyond yield, stiffness continued to decrease until failure occurred.

The data in Figure 5(a) show that when the nonfatigued specimens were cooled to 0°C, the stiffness, both before and after the yield point, increased, but on further cooling to -40°C, they decreased. It is probable that the behavior of the matrix, which becomes stiffer

Figure 6. Low-temperature flexural performance data of the fatigued specimens.

Figure 6 (a) shows the comparison of the flexural modulus of fatigued specimens both before (upper curve) and after (lower curve) the yield point. It is clear that the post-yield flexural modulus drops dramatically at all temperatures. This is expected because of a large accumulation of microdamage.

Figure 5(c) shows a comparison of the pre-yield flexural modulus data for the nonfatigued (upper curve) and the fatigued (lower curve) samples. A reduction of modulus is expected for the fatigued samples, but apparently this reduction is not significant at room temperature (20°C). It is only at lower temperatures that the difference is more significant. It can be inferred that the low-temperature-induced microcracking/debonding probably has a more dominating effect in reducing the composite's overall stiffness than the load cycling alone.

3.3 Strength:

Strength data of nonfatigued specimens are shown in Figure 5 (b), and those of fatigued specimens in Figure 6 (b). Figure 7(a) shows the same data of the yield strength values as illustrated in Figures 5(b) and 6(b), but superimposed for clarity. Similarly, Figure 7(b) shows the failure strength values. At room temperature, the failure strength associated with fatigued panels was nearly identical to that of the nonfatigued specimens. As temperatures decreased however, dramatic differences in strength became apparent [Figure 7(a)]. Microdamage produced during the fatigue process seemed to strengthen the material. We have discussed before that, in all cases, fracture was initiated with the growth of incipient interlaminar microcracks tending to split the specimen horizontally in layers. The onset of these cracks corresponded to the yield point. The yield strength (for all temperatures), was less than the corresponding yield strength for nonfatigued specimens, which suggests that microdamage influenced the yield. We also have postulated before that microdamage also reduced the stiffness both before and after yield. The final failure, which requires through-the-thickness fiber fracture both in tensile and compressive modes, (compressive fracture by itself will not cause complete failure), must reflect the fiber failure strength in tension. It is not totally inconceivable that, following cyclic loading, the reduction in matrix stiffness allowed the fibers to attain more uniform stress distribution, therefore allowing higher failure loads. At lower temperatures, more microdamage is expected due to the higher residual thermoelastic stresses resulting from the thermal ex-

Figure 7. Comparison of flexural strengths of fatigued and nonfatigued specimens.

pansion mismatches. Larger reductions in pre-yield and post-yield stiffnesses support this observation. Thus, both low temperature and load cycling seem to have a beneficial effect on the flexural strength of the uniaxial laminate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Although numerous models of damage mechanisms and accumulation under fatigue loading are available in composites literature, most, however, do not account for the influence of lower temperatures. The results from flexural fatigue tests, presented here, show evidence of nonmonotonic changes in residual strength and stiffness upon progressive cooling. Strength increased but stiffness degraded with lower temperatures. By describing the failure process, the constituent's low-temperature properties and thermoelastic stresses are shown to be the factors for such paradoxical results. Although it is true that interlaminar forces will come into play while considering more quasi-isotropic laminates with multiple orientations, the influence of low temperatures on the intraply mechanism of failure, as discussed above, must be considered to apply fatigue damage models in low temperature regimes. Moreover, because the compressive strength is much lower than the tensile strength, flexural fatigue is controlled by the compressive strength. Low temperature enhances the strength and stiffness of the matrix, and thus provides the overall beneficial effects on flexural fatigue.

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